

Silhouette plots and dendrogram

Clustering summary. We clustered tasks by their appraisal signatures. For each task, we computed **top-2** agreement proportions (share selecting 4–5 on a 5-point scale [1]) for Value, Identity, Accountability, and Demands, then standardized them to (z)-scores for cross-scale comparability [2]. We applied agglomerative hierarchical clustering with Ward’s linkage [3] on Euclidean distances of the (z)-scores. The optimal ($k=3$) was selected via average silhouette analysis [4] (Fig.S1).

Figure S1. Silhouette analysis for Ward’s hierarchical clustering of task-appraisal signatures (z-scored top-2 agreement proportions across four appraisals). Average silhouette scores are shown for $k=2-6$; the peak at ($k=3$) supports a 3-cluster solution.

Robustness. Inputs were precision-weighted (inverse-variance shrinkage toward the grand mean) to temper unequal task (N)s; cluster stability was assessed via stratified bootstraps ($B=1000$) [2]. The analysis yielded the following clusters:

Figure S2. Hierarchical clustering dendrogram (Ward linkage) on Euclidean distances between task-appraisal signatures. The red dashed line indicates the cut producing $k=3$ clusters; branch colors show cluster membership for the tasks.

References

- [1] Riadh Ladhari. 2010. Developing e-service quality scales: A literature review. *Journal of retailing and consumer services* 17, 6 (2010), 464–477.
- [2] Joseph F Hair. 2009. *Multivariate data analysis*. (2009).
- [3] Joe H Ward Jr. 1963. Hierarchical grouping to optimize an objective function. *Journal of the American statistical association* 58, 301 (1963), 236–244.
- [4] Peter J Rousseeuw. 1987. Silhouettes: a graphical aid to the interpretation and validation of cluster analysis. *Journal of computational and applied mathematics* 20 (1987), 53–65.